

THE ASSUMPTION OF THE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Rustamova Dilbar Rustamovna

Department of social humanities,
Tashkent State University of Economics,
Senior Lecturer

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8287419>

Abstract. *Why international economic organizations were actually formed. Were they really needed, this article will talk about the formation of international economic organizations, their essence, tasks and responsibilities, international economic organizations*

Keywords: *international economic organizations, economic relations, World Trade, Economic Development, Cooperation, globalization, crisis.*

ПРИНЯТИЕ НА СЕБЯ ОТВЕТСТВЕННОСТИ ЗА ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ

Аннотация. *Почему на самом деле были созданы международные экономические организации. Были ли они действительно нужны, в этой статье пойдет речь о формировании международных экономических организаций, их сущности, задачах и ответственности, международных экономических организациях*

Ключевые слова: *международные экономические организации, экономические отношения, Мировая торговля, экономическое развитие, сотрудничество, глобализация, кризис.*

One of the most important parts of economic development is the successful establishment of economic relations between countries. Therefore, after World War II, there was a need for international economic organizations for the purpose of exchange of goods, labor, scientific information, labor between states. Economic relations have improved from the developed rules of organizations regulating international economic relations and their constant observations.

What is actually understood by taking control of economic relations between states. Economic relations between member states of an international economic organization create a number of rules and obligations. The shift in control of customs duties for freedom for international trade, the increasing global problems, the growing global economy, the strengthening of ties between states, the crisis that followed the policy of oil-supplying countries of the late 20th century, and the commitment to ensure the growth of independent states.

International Organization analysis is the legal, economic, political and social analysis of global organizations. This article provides an analysis of the changes in international organizations, their main tasks and roles, generally accepted forms of membership in them, Uzbek and international political, economic and legal analysis of their activities, their international content and concepts, interaction with international organizations, the important importance of regulating their problems and its results, shortcomings of international organizations, the quality of their activities and the International organizations, information and statistics on the situation in the world, in particular on the basis of papers and State, important information of the system of international organizations, quality confirmation organizations of international knowledge, Organization of expressive organizations and their activities of native, international organizations,

goals of international development and management in international organizations, analysis of international organizations and their development potentials have been given.

An analysis of the importance of working with international organizations in everyday life, the problems associated with their changes, the information doctrine of international organizations and the labor doctrine of international organizations is given. Also, an analysis was given on the stage of changes in international organizations, their development, features of the general information informatization of international organizations, their social and political consequences. During the article, the use of the criteria of information used by international organizations, their informational qualities and information mechanisms in the system of international organizations are described.

The problems of international organizations on regulation, membership and cooperation with international organizations on Uzbek law, their legal positions and analysis of the integrated activities of international organizations in the economic sphere in Uzbekistan belong. The article describes the role of international organizations in international knowledge, cooperation with international organizations, important organizations for changing the adaptation of diplomas of their activities on the territory of Uzbekistan, their importance, and the analysis on the problem of changes in international organizations and their danger from the legal side of Uzbekistan has been carried out.

The main activity of international economic organizations consists in identifying the problems arising in the contacts of member countries between states, working on their solutions. That is, to discuss the existing problems together and make decisions to make them. Regulation, control and implementation are functions of international organizations. There are two views on the typology of international economic organizations: the likes of geographically large-scale international economic relations and large-scale activities. It will be advisable to separately consider the territorial and global structures that have come from the criteria for international relations of a large geographical scale.

For the development of international economic relations between states, it was necessary to establish trade with other countries. For this reason, the main goal of international economic organizations was to regulate economic relations between states under international treaties, work on them, develop new laws, regulate economic relations between them by making amendments to them. The economic problems of countries that are part of an international economic organization are heard and it is the task of such organizations to solve the problems that have arisen in this area, to consider the solutions to the problem and, together with this, to implement them.

Analysis of international organizations is based on the process of studying the documentation of problem and logical theories that arise in the activities of international organizations. This analysis analyzes issues related to international law, justice, democracy, human rights, diplomacy, world economy, etc. Analysis of international organizations, ensuring its successful work in the world system of organizations, providing inter-organizational control and reporting, analyzing skills in the field of international organizations through email, the internet, etc., helps to protect the unity of thoughts in the process and ensure positive changes in global relations. The analysis of international organizations requires that international organizations increase the direct influence of states in their participation other than one-on-one issues.

The analysis of international organizations is also used to organize the necessary opportunities for strengthening the image of the world's States. Analysis of international organizations requires assistance in the development of international Orientalism and its interaction, opens up the possibility of further development of the economy, diplomacy, society and other spheres of states. The main tasks of the analysis are to further enhance the cooperation of international organizations with one of the countries and to help strengthen their ties.

REFERENCES

1. A.Vaxabov, Sh. Xajibakiyev, Sh. Raxmonov, X. Usmanova,2014, Jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro iqtisodiy munosabatlar.
2. G.Nazarova, X. Xalilov, A. Azimov, I. Xanova, 2010, Xalqaro iqtisodiy integratsiya.
3. USED INTERNET DATA.